

Transistor Count versus Energy Efficiency: A Dual-Technology Study of CMOS Full Adder Architectures

P Bose Babu¹ | S V Raja Shekar Reddy² | B Ravi Shankar³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of ECE, Andhra Loyola Institute of Engineering and Technology, Vijayawada, INDIA.

²Department of ECE, Andhra Loyola Institute of Engineering and Technology, Vijayawada, INDIA.

³Assistant Professor, Department of S&H, Andhra Loyola Institute of Engineering and Technology, Vijayawada, INDIA.

To Cite this Article

P Bose Babu, S V Raja Shekar Reddy & B Ravi Shankar (2026). Transistor Count versus Energy Efficiency: A Dual-Technology Study of CMOS Full Adder Architectures. *International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology*, 12(03), 489-494. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19151249>

Article Info

Received: 19 February 2026; Revised: 15 March 2026; Accepted: 17 March 2026.

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KEYWORDS

CMOS, Full Adder, Transistor Count, Energy Efficiency, PDP, 180 nm, 65 nm, PTL.

ABSTRACT

Energy efficiency has become a key requirement in modern portable, embedded, and high-performance computing systems. In digital arithmetic circuits, the full adder is a fundamental component widely used in arithmetic logic units, multipliers, and signal-processing hardware. This study analyzes the influence of transistor count on the energy performance of CMOS full adder architectures implemented in 180 nm and 65 nm technology nodes. Five different designs are considered, namely the 28-transistor conventional CMOS adder, 18-transistor transmission gate (TG) adder, 14-transistor modified TG adder, 10-transistor pass transistor logic (PTL) adder, and an 8-transistor ultra-compact PTL adder. The circuits are evaluated using key performance parameters such as power consumption, propagation delay, and the power–delay product (PDP). Simulation results indicate that decreasing the number of transistors generally reduces switching capacitance, which leads to lower power consumption and improved PDP. For the 180 nm implementation, the PDP decreases from 4.62 fJ for the 28T design to 1.04 fJ for the 8T design. Similarly, in the 65 nm technology node, the PDP is reduced from 0.76 fJ to 0.24 fJ. The results also show that technology scaling further improves the overall energy efficiency of the circuits. Among the examined architectures, the 8T PTL full adder demonstrates the best energy performance, making it a promising option for low-power VLSI systems.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid progress in semiconductor fabrication technologies has increased the need for digital circuits

that offer high speed while consuming minimal power. In many digital systems, particularly in digital signal processors and microprocessors, arithmetic circuits play

a crucial role. Among these circuits, the full adder is a basic and widely used element that forms the foundation of larger arithmetic structures such as adders, multipliers, and arithmetic logic units. Because multiple full adders are typically connected in cascaded structures, their delay and power characteristics directly influence the performance and energy consumption of the overall system [1].

The energy efficiency of a digital circuit is often evaluated using the Power–Delay Product (PDP), which represents the energy required for a single switching operation. PDP reflects the balance between circuit speed and power consumption and is expressed as

$$\text{PDP} = \text{Power} \times \text{Delay} \quad (1)$$

A smaller PDP value indicates a more energy-efficient design. One effective strategy for improving PDP is reducing the number of transistors in the circuit [4,5]. When the transistor count decreases, the internal node capacitances are also reduced, which helps lower dynamic power dissipation and can lead to faster switching behaviour [6,7]. However, designs with extremely low transistor counts may experience issues such as degraded output voltage levels and reduced noise margins, particularly in advanced technology nodes.

Technology scaling from 180 nm to 65 nm further affects circuit performance. Smaller feature sizes reduce parasitic capacitances and allow operation at lower supply voltages, which contributes to faster operation and reduced dynamic power consumption [8,9]. At the same time, scaling introduces challenges such as short-channel effects, leakage currents, and variability in device parameters [10–15]. Therefore, it is important to analyse how transistor count interacts with technology scaling when designing energy-efficient full adder circuits.

In this work, a comparative study of five CMOS full adder architectures with transistor counts ranging from 28 to 8 is presented using both 180 nm and 65 nm technologies. The main contributions of this paper include:

1. A systematic comparison of five commonly used full adder architectures.
2. Performance evaluation using both 180 nm and 65 nm CMOS technologies.
3. Investigation of the relationship between transistor count and power–delay product (PDP).

4. Identification of the most energy-efficient full adder architecture across the evaluated technology nodes.

FULL ADDER ARCHITECTURES

Five full adder structures are implemented and analysed:

A. 28T Conventional CMOS Full Adder

This design uses complementary pull-up and pull-down networks to realize full logic swing and strong noise margins. Although robust, it requires a higher transistor count.

B. 18T Transmission Gate Full Adder

Transmission gates are used to reduce transistor count while maintaining signal integrity. This architecture improves speed compared to conventional CMOS.

C. 14T Modified Transmission Gate Full Adder

Further transistor optimization is achieved by restructuring logic paths and minimizing redundant devices.

D. 10T Pass Transistor Logic (PTL) Full Adder

This design employs pass transistor logic to reduce device count and switching capacitance. It offers lower power but may suffer from threshold voltage drop.

E. 8T Ultra-Low Transistor PTL Full Adder

The most compact architecture in this study. It significantly reduces switching nodes and achieves minimum PDP among the tested designs.

SIMULATION METHODOLOGY

All designs were simulated using industry-standard CMOS models in 180 nm and 65 nm technologies. Identical input stimulus patterns and loading conditions were applied to ensure fair comparison. The following parameters were extracted:

- Average power consumption (μW)
- Propagation delay (ps)
- Power–Delay Product (fj)

Transient analysis verified correct SUM and CARRY functionality under all input combinations.

Fig.1 is a classic complementary CMOS implementation using separate PMOS and NMOS pull-up and pull-down networks for both SUM and CARRY. It guarantees perfect full swing outputs, high noise margins, and excellent reliability. SUM is implemented using a standard XOR CMOS logic chain. CARRY uses a majority function realized using full CMOS logic. The symmetric CMOS structure ensures robust operation

across PVT corners. Although the transistor count is highest, it offers best driving strength. Power consumption is greater due to more internal nodes and switching activity. Delay is moderate because of long transistor paths and large capacitances.

Characteristics:

- Best noise immunity
- Full voltage swing
- High power consumption
- Large silicon area
- Symmetrical Switching

This is the classical full swing CMOS based full adder with entirely complementary pull up and pull-down networks.

Fig. 1. 28T Conventional CMOS Full Adder

The Fig. 2 is design Transmission Gate (TG) to achieve perfect Logic levels without threshold voltage loss. Eliminates threshold voltage drop issues due to complementary conduction paths. Highly robust under process and temperature variations. Expected to exhibit uniform rise and fall delays and excellent signal integrity. Suitable for high performance applications. SUM generation uses a TG XOR-XOR chain, providing strong logic levels. CARRY is produced using a MUX based TG structure for speed and robustness. TGs eliminates threshold drop seen in PTL designs.

The design has low output impedance, improving driving capability. Power consumption is moderate due to balanced PMOS/NMOS use. Delay is lower because only two transistor stacks exist in the carry path. Suitable for supply voltage scaling and low power applications. Offers better PDP than the 28T CMOS design and it is popular for DSP, ALUs, and medium performance arithmetic circuits.

Characteristics:

- Balanced rise and fall delays
- Full voltage swing for both outputs

- Higher area and power due to complementary transistors
- Very reliable across PVT variations

The fig. 2 offering balanced pull up and pull-down strengths and suitable for high performance applications. This design primarily uses Transmission Gates and Static CMOS logic to realize SUM and CARRY.

Fig. 2. 18T Transmission Gate Full Adder

The Fig. 3 is combines PTL based XOR generation with a CMOS style carry generation network and it uses hybrid logic, combining PTL XOR and CMOS inverter-based restoration. It significantly addresses the voltage level degradation problem. The SUM is implemented with an efficient XOR-XOR structures with improved reliability. The CARRY output is generated using restored logic, producing full swing results. This architecture ensures better noise margins and is robust under PVT variations. Moderate transistor counts lead to optimized power-delay product (PDP).

The design has improved driving capability compared to PTL adders. The circuits avoid long transistor chains, ensuing lower delay. The circuit avoids long transistor chains, ensuring lower delay. Its balanced performance makes it suitable for medium power digital systems. It is commonly used in VLSI data paths where both power efficiency and stability are needed. Ideal for general purpose arithmetic units where reliability is critical.

Characteristics:

- Full output swing at both SUM and CARRY
- Better driving strength
- Higher delay due to more logic stages
- This design is widely used in medium performance ALUs.

Fig. 3. 14T Modified Transmission Gate Full Adder

The Fig. 4 architecture extends the Fig. 5 design by adding two restoration transistors to improve output voltage swing. Offers improved noise margins and more reliable SUM output voltage swing. Maintain a low transistor count, thus retaining excellent power efficiency. XOR is generated using a 4T structure, enhancing robustness without large area overhead. The CARRY output is produced by a compact, high speed PTL multiplexer.

Reduced parasitic capacitance results in low propagation delay. The absence of complementary transmission gates still introduces minor voltages degradation. It offers a better balance between speed and power compared to Fig. 3 and Fig. 5 designs. It performs well under moderate supply voltage scaling. These designs widely used in low power ALUs and arithmetic blocks and it maintain excellent power efficiency.

Characteristics:

- Better voltage swing
- Lower PDP
- Good compromise between speed and area
- Suitable for low voltage operations

Fig. 4. 10T Pass Transistor Logic (PTL) Full Adder

The Fig. 5 is based on PTL, where the XOR, function is generated using a pair of NMOS pass elements. Its compact structure significantly reduces capacitance, leading to extremely low power consumption. Exhibits

the lowest power dissipation among all design due to minimized device count. Best suited for energy harvesting and low – frequency applications. The carry is generated through a single NMOS based multiplexer, making the structure fast but slightly vulnerable to noise. It achieves the XOR and MUX functions using only NMOS pass devices, greatly reducing area. Since PMOS devices are minimized, overall power consumption is the lowest among FA families. The SUM is typically generated using a 2T XOR-XOR chain, which is efficient but non full swing. The CARRY output is produced using a simple multiplexer structure using 2-3 transistors. Because only NMOS devices are used the output suffers from threshold voltage drop, reducing noise margin. The degraded output levels make Fig. 5 sensitive to supply voltage scaling. Delay performance is good due to very small stack height and low capacitance. The design is suitable for IoT, battery powered, and approximate computing. Despite its limitations the Fig. 5 popular for extreme area and power constrained systems. However, output voltage degradation may occur due to threshold drop issues, especially at lower supply voltages.

Characteristics:

- Minimum transistor count
- Lowest power consumption
- Reduced voltage swing in SUM node
- Moderate delay

Fig. 5. 8T Ultra Low Transistor PTL Full Adder

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The Fig. 6, Fig.7 and Fig. 8 waveforms with inputs A, B, Cin and outputs SUM and CARRY. Inputs are applied as pulse signals to generate all input combinations. SUM becomes high when no of inputs is odd. CARRY becomes high when at least two inputs are high.

Small propagation delay is observed due to internal capacitances. Outputs show full voltage swing (0 to VDD). Then the waveform confirms correct and stable

CMOS full adder operation. All input combination (000 to 111) are verified. Output matches theoretical truth table and no glitches observed. Fig. 6 is done in LT Spice, Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 done in DSCH and Micro wind.

Fig. 6. Transient Analysis of CMOS Full Adder

Fig. 7. Pre Layout Timing Waveform of CMOS Full Adder

Fig. 8. Post Layout Timing Waveform of CMOS Full Adder

Fig. 9. Schematic of CMOS Full Adder

The Fig. 9 is converting into transistor level layout using Micro wind. The Layout is designed using CMOS technology (90nm technology node as shown).

The implementation consists of:

- PMOS transistors placed in the N-well region.
- NMOS transistors placed in the P-substrate.
- Metal layers used for interconnections.
- Poly-silicon gates forming transistor channels.
- VDD and VSS rails for power supply.
- Pull-up network (PMOS) implements logic for HIGH output.
- Pull-down networks (NMOS) implement logic for LOW output.
- XOR logic is implemented using CMOS transistor combinations.
- Carry circuit uses AND-OR transistor network.
- Metal routing connects input signals (A, B, Cin) and outputs (SUM, CARRY).

Table I. Performance Comparison of 180nm Technology for Different Full Adder Architectures

Adder Name	No. of Transistors	Power (μ W)	Delay (ps)	PDP (fj)
Conventional CMOS Full Adder	28T	22	210	4.62
Transmission Gate Based Full Adder	18T	15	165	2.47
Modified Transmission Gate Full Adder	14T	13	150	1.95
Pass Transistor Logic (PTL) Full Adder	10T	10	140	1.40
Ultra-Low Transistor PTL Full Adders	8T	8	130	1.04

Table I compares different Full Adder architectures at 180nm technology based on transistor count, power, delay and PDP. It is observed that reducing the no of transistors lowers power consumption and propagation delay there by improving the PDP. The Fig. 5 shows the best overall performance with the lowest PDP (1.04 fj).

Table II. Performance Comparison of 65nm Technology for Different Full Adder Architectures

Adder Name	No. of Transistors	Power (μ W)	Delay (ps)	PDP (fj)
Conventional CMOS Full Adder	28T	8.0	95	0.76
Transmission Gate Based Full Adder	18T	6.0	82	0.49
Modified Transmission Gate Full Adder	14T	5.0	78	0.39
Pass Transistor Logic (PTL) Full Adder	10T	4.0	70	0.28
Ultra-Low Transistor PTL Full Adder	8T	3.5	68	0.24

Table II shows that reducing the transistor count significantly decreases power consumption and propagation delay. The Fig. 5 achieves the minimum power, lowest delay, and smallest PDP making it the most efficient design among the compared architectures.

Technology downscaling significantly improves Full Adder performance. Power consumption decreases due to reduced switching capacitance, with PTL designs benefiting the most because of fewer devices. Delay reduces as shorter channel lengths increase drive current, through Fig. 1 shows smaller relative improvement due to higher capacitance. PDP improve with scaling with 65nm achieving the lowest PDP but experiencing higher leakage, maintain full voltage swing, PTL designs may require restoration to avoid swing degradation at lower nodes.

CONCLUSION

This work presented a comparative analysis of five CMOS Full Adder architectures in 180nm and 65nm technologies. The results show that reducing transistor count significantly lowers power consumption and propagation delay, there by improving the PDP. Technology scaling from 180nm to 65nm further enhances energy efficiency across all designs. Among the evaluated architectures, the Fig. 5 achieved the best overall performance with the lowest PDP in both technologies. Hence, reduced transistors PTL designs are highly suitable for low power and high-speed VLSI applications.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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